

Communications Reliability of Tactical Wideband Radio Systems

Kenneth H. Brockel and Victor J. Procopio
(908) 544-2077

Space and Terrestrial Communications Directorate
U.S. Army Communications-Electronics Command
Fort Monmouth, New Jersey 07703-5203

William T. Barnett and Arvids Vigants
Telos Corporation
656 Shrewsbury Avenue
Shrewsbury, New Jersey 07702

Introduction

The digitized battlefield requires communications realism in modeling and simulation. It also requires the capability for broadband wireless communications provided by high-capacity digital radio (HCDR). A goal of current Army wireless communications programs is to achieve seamless digital connectivity between all communications platforms. There is no program that considers the time-varying error performance of mobile wireless links that provide connectivity. The development of narrowband error-burst models and their real-time simulation, and the development of wideband link performance models described in this paper address that void. This program leverages technology and models for line-of-sight (LOS) communications links developed by the Space and Terrestrial Communications Directorate (S&TCD) of the U.S. Army Communications-Electronics Command (CECOM) Research, Development and Engineering Center and Telos Corporation.

The significance of time-varying propagation was a lesson learned from recent operations in Southwest Asia. A major performance issue for stationary LOS links was the severe time-varying reduction of received signal strength (RSS) caused by layering of the atmosphere, often referred to as ducting. A link reliability working group was convened by S&TCD to

develop a channel model for planning and engineering current narrowband tactical radio systems. The channel model [1] and its accompanying database of world climate factors [2] have been incorporated into a new automated battlefield Network Planning Terminal, initially fielded in 2QFY94 by the Army Project Manager, Joint Tactical Area Communications Systems as part of Mobile Subscriber Equipment (MSE) [3,4].

Communications problems on a digitized battlefield will often stem from radio sources. As forces move across the battlefield, the quality of radio connections between them varies dramatically and continually as a function of terrain, propagation, climate, radio-link capabilities, and other factors. These variations, which cause time-varying error bursts in the digital bit stream, are generally not accounted for in current algorithms, models, methods, or simulations of tactical communications, or have been included only as averages. Communications realism that includes the effects of time-varying error bursts is needed to accurately describe delays and interruptions of command and control (C2) information. Commanders must also have a means for assessing the impact of communications realism. Real-time simulation provides such a means. *To be of value, communications-effects models and simulations must faithfully reproduce the radio connectivity and network effects that forces will encounter as they maneuver across the battlefield.* No communications-effects model, including existing real-time channel simulators, currently provides the necessary degree of fidelity. The real-time simulation described in this paper addresses these issues.

This work has been sponsored by the Improved Spectrum Efficiency Modeling and Simulation (ISEMS) project of the Space and Terrestrial Communications Directorate (S&TCD) of the Research, Development and Engineering Center (RDEC), U.S. Army Communications-Electronics Command (CECOM).

The C2 information needs of the digitized battlefield (voice, data, and imagery) dictate the need for a network employing on-the-move high-capacity wireless communications. The performance of these wideband links relative to narrowband links will be additionally impacted by propagation-imposed distortion of the transmitted signal spectrum (dispersion). This phenomenon does not affect current tactical digital radios because information rates are low and channel bandwidths are small. The goals of the program outlined in this paper are to ensure that wideband on-the-move tactical radios can accommodate dispersion and be built to satisfy Army needs. The HCDR is intended to be a nondevelopmental item, with initial fielding of a scalable prototype for the digitized battlefield in fiscal year 1996.

This paper describes CECOM efforts in the areas of realistic communications-channel modeling, real-time simulation of the on-the-move tactical communications, and an HCDR communications performance model. The paper concludes with an illustration of using the digital radio performance model to determine maximum link lengths.

Channel Error-Burst Models

The first part of channel error-burst model development will describe the physical mechanisms that cause degraded communications. The principal effects are short- and long-term variations of RSS. These variations need to be described as functions of time and frequency.

Physical Mechanisms

Terminal movement means that RSS varies continuously and randomly because the receiver is always exposed to multiple replicas of the transmitted signal that interact destructively. The replicas are signal returns from structures, hills, foliage, and atmospheric layers. *Models for terrain-associated propagation loss do not account for these replicas.* These models estimate the long-term root-mean-square (rms) value of the received signal. In reality, the received signal varies dynamically and is at times tens of dB weaker than its rms value. This causes error bursts in the digital bit stream.

In channel modeling, the replicas of the signal are described as separate rays of energy that reach the receiver. Essential communications effects become readily apparent from an examination of theoretical two-ray interaction. In two-ray interaction, RSS varies periodically as a function of frequency (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Interaction of Two Rays

On-the-move communications receivers in a real environment receive more than two rays, as illustrated in Figure 2. The multiple rays create a complicated signal-strength structure in space, time, and frequency. The disturbances of the spectrum become random as opposed to the orderly pattern in Figure 1.

Figure 2. Multiple Received Components for One Transmitted Signal

The time rate of the RSS variations increases with vehicle speed. There can also be RSS variations when vehicles are stationary because phase balances of the interacting rays change as other vehicles move, as foliage moves in the wind, and, on longer paths, because atmospheric layers are dynamic. Typical fading of a 900-MHz signal received by a mobile unit traveling at 15 mph is shown in Figure 3 [5]. The signal strength ranges over tens of dBs, and there are many signal minima in a one-second interval. It is obvious that digital or analog transmissions would be severely impacted.

Figure 3. On-the-Move Signal Variation

Error Bursts

The digital output from a radio system subjected to rapidly varying RSS (see Figure 3) will have corresponding bit-error behavior. Every time RSS crosses the radio system's performance threshold, the digital stream will have an unacceptable burst of errors in which a random bit stream replaces the desired one (see Figure 4). These error bursts occur randomly and have varying lengths.

Figure 4. Error-Burst Variability

Table 1. Error-Burst Statistics

Channel Reliability Percent	Required Fade Margin dB	Number of Error Bursts per Minute	Average Burst Duration Milliseconds
30 MHz, 15 Miles/Hour:			
90	10	29	198
99	20	10	60
99.9	30	3	19
88 MHz, 15 Miles/Hour:			
90	10	85	67
99	20	29	20
99.9	30	9	6
435 MHz, 15 Miles/Hour:			
90	10	418	14
99	20	145	4
99.9	30	46	1.3

Table 1 provides an idealized stochastic example of burst-error behavior for different channel reliabilities at Single Channel Ground and Airborne Radio System (SINCGARS) and Enhanced Position Location Reporting System (EPLRS) frequencies for a simple radio on a platform moving at 15 mph. For a 30-MHz radio with a system margin of 10 dB, there are 29 error bursts per minute with an average duration of 200 milliseconds – an average of one burst every two seconds – impairing 10 percent of the data.

MIL-STD-188-220 Modeling

Communications on a digitized battlefield are principally data communications. The universally accepted frame of reference for network architecture and protocol standards in data communications is the Open Systems Interconnection (OSI) model. The communications functions in the OSI model are partitioned into seven layers (physical, data link, network, transport, session, presentation, and application). The U.S. Army has developed a data communications standard (MIL-STD-188-220) to resolve interoperability issues encountered during Operation Desert Storm. The communications functions in this standard correspond to only five of the seven OSI layers (physical, data link, network, presentation, and application). MIL-STD-188-220 has been selected as the objective protocol for digitizing the battlefield.

System performance models (SPMs) for a number of military communications systems have been developed at the CECOM RDEC. The latest is the Combined Arms Command and Control (CAC2) SPM. This model accepts mission threads, produces communications traffic loads, and provides information about throughput and grade of service for a modeled network. The CAC2 SPM includes the MIL-STD-188-220 model.

Incorporation of communications realism in the SPMs and in the modeling of MIL-STD-188-220 is under consideration. Inclusion of error bursts would increase the fidelity of the models and allow better evaluation of the effectiveness of MIL-STD-188-220.

Real-Time Simulation

Communications between moving platforms in different networks on the digital battlefield requires enhancement of Army communications systems. A target for CECOM is realistic, real-time, soldier-in-the-loop simulation, which is needed to devise and evaluate such enhancements. The concepts and exploratory software developed for the simulation can

also be used by Army organizations to expose commanders, soldiers, and research and development personnel to communications realism in new battle scenarios, train soldiers, and simulate performance of potential future communications equipment. This section describes proposed real-time on-the-move communications modeling, implementation of the models, and operation of the simulation.

Radio Links and the Environment

The real-time simulation components of an on-the-move radio link are depicted in Figure 5. The simulation blocks contain a mix of new and SPM-derived parts. The blocks must be compact in order to meet computation-time constraints of real-time simulations. Environmental effects in the simulation are stochastically generated. For example, multipath fading events (Figure 6) for application to frequency hopping in EPLRS are generated by random processes with correlation in time and frequency. Observation of the multipath performance of systems based on pseudo-

Figure 5. On-the-Move Radio: Single-Link Characteristics

Figure 6. Multipath Events in Time-Frequency Plane

random noise techniques (frequency hopping and spread spectrum) for interference-limited environments is of particular interest.

Model Implementation

Simulated networks of four platforms (vehicles) are used to explore the effects of communications realism on networks and information exchange between platforms in different networks. An example of a simulation involving two different but interconnected networks (EPLRS and SINCGARS) is illustrated in Figure 7. Network effects (access and message delays) are provided by traffic information obtained from appropriate SPMs.

Figure 7. Simulation Example

A tactical multinet gateway (TMG) must provide protocol conversion and multiplexing functions. In the example in Figure 7, the simulated gateway also provides higher-echelon messages, a description of radio-frequency interference (RFI), and electronic jamming control (real-time by operator or prerecorded). The TMG is a commercial off-the-shelf internet protocol router.

Each vehicle (including its radio) and the gateway are simulated by separate computers. The locations of the vehicles are displayed on each computer screen over a map background that includes the battlefield environment. A soldier at the computer “drives” the vehicle in real time by moving a trackball or joystick to simulate vehicle movement over an exercise area. Real-time voice and data communications are available to the soldier through speakers and on-screen message windows. The soldier communicates with the other soldiers/operators by following standard communications operating procedures for the systems being modeled.

The computers contain identical communications-realism and network-effects software and databases. The databases contain precomputed propagation-path-loss and SPM-generated background communications-traffic-load information. This reduces the real-time computation load. The communications effects are generated locally in each computer. High fidelity in the simulation is achieved by real-time computation of link budgets and error-burst effects. This approach provides network effects in a way that permits the soldiers to have real-time control of their simulated vehicles using modest computer resources.

Distributed Interactive Simulation (DIS) Version 1.0 concepts are used in the simulation implementation to achieve simulation interoperability. The DIS infrastructure provides the standards to support systems, technologies, and platforms from the various services and defines how to link simulations at multiple locations via protocol data units to create realistic simulation of highly interactive activities.

HCDR Link Performance and Technology Targets

The LOS radio link characteristics requiring planning targets are link path length, path reliability, information capacity of the radio channel, bandwidth, and operating radio frequency.

Asynchronous transfer mode (ATM)-to-ATM switch interconnections, with both ends stationary, will need 20-to-40-km link lengths [6]. A mobile radio access point (RAP) to a stationary ATM will need 1-to-20-km link lengths. The path reliability target, drawn from MSE objectives for critical links, is 99.9 percent for a link operating at any time of year in any location worldwide.

Information needs on the digitized battlefield and digital communication standards determine the radio-channel communications capacity. The per-channel capacity of each HCDR is expected to be between 44.736 and 155.52 Mbps. The latter rate is the lowest in the digital synchronous hierarchy. The target capacity, therefore, is 156 Mbps. Spectral efficiency of 4 bits/Hz is a target derived from commercial practice, which calls for 64 QAM. This requires a 40-MHz radio bandwidth for the 156-Mbps payload. Hardware feasibility and spectrum-management practice dictate that bandwidth be no larger than one percent of the radio frequency; therefore, a radio frequency of 4 GHz or higher is required. In order to avoid a significant impact of rain attenuation, the radio frequency should be less than 8 GHz.

For ATM-to-ATM connectivity, the target HCDR link is, therefore, a 156-Mbps, 64-QAM radio operating in a 40-MHz bandwidth at a frequency between 4 and 8 GHz, able to achieve 99.9-percent path reliability and link-length maximums of 40 km operating at any location worldwide at any time. For ATM-to-RAP (one end on the move), the target HCDR is a 45-Mbps, 4-QAM, 40-MHz bandwidth radio or a 45-Mbps, 16-QAM, 20-MHz bandwidth radio with a maximum path length of 20 km; other characteristics remain unchanged. Power, size, and weight targets have yet to be established but are not expected to be restrictive.

Channel Dispersion Models

Potential designs for a digital radio capable of meeting requirements for a high-capacity on-the-move application need to consider the radio's sensitivity to time-varying dispersion. For example, an increase in transmitter power will have no benefit when the predominant error cause is intersymbol interference resulting from dispersion. Transmitter power can only overcome the effects of thermal and RFI noise.

Figure 8. Path-Length Difference, Meters

The signal-strength minima, referred to as notches (see Figure 1), have a frequency separation that is a function of the path-length difference of the two rays, as shown in Figure 8. The path-length differences of refracted rays in on-the-move links are larger than those in stationary links because on-the-move links are generally shorter, and reflections can be generated by man-made or natural objects near the ends of the link (see Figure 2). The rays are not nearly parallel; the resulting refracted ray path-length difference is large. The notch separation is 3 MHz for a representative

path-length difference of 100 meters (from Figure 8). Assuming that a 10-MHz bandwidth defines the lower limit of wideband, the conclusion is that because notch separation is smaller than the channel bandwidth, dispersion for wideband on-the-move channels will be severe and must be modeled to include multiple notches.

A measured example of a notch in frequency caused by atmospheric multipath is shown in Figure 9. The delay spread associated with such notches is small. A widely used model to analytically represent such dispersion for the purpose of system performance description uses a delay of 6.3 ns. A useful parameter to relate bit-error-ratio (BER) performance to dispersive fading is the in-band power difference (IBPD), the amplitude spread in a specified bandwidth (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Dispersion and In-Band Power Difference

Methods have been developed to describe path reliability as a function of the distributions of RSS and IBPD. Sample distributions are illustrated in Figure 10. A radio system operating over this channel experiences an accumulated outage of a few hundred seconds because of thermal-noise effects (for a fade margin of 34 dB). Operating without adaptive dynamic equalization, this system experiences additional accumulated outage of a few thousand seconds because of dispersion. In this case, dispersion clearly dominates performance (IBPD margin of 8 dB). The addition of commercially available dynamic equalization to a 64-QAM digital radio typically improves the IBPD margin to 15 dB. The corresponding dispersive fade margin is 30 dB (from Figure 11), as defined by the common probability intercept on the IBPD and single-frequency fade-depth distributions.

Figure 10. Measured Fading and IBPD Distributions

Figure 11. Fading and IBPD Distributions

Comprehensive methods, some of which have been mentioned in this paper, have been developed for dispersion design of commercial LOS wideband links. These links are stationary, and have single in-band notches and small delay spreads. Wideband on-the-move systems are not stationary, and have multiple in-band notches and large delay spreads. Dispersion modeling for stationary wideband systems serves as a guide for modeling dispersion and its effects on outage and error-burst dynamics for on-the-move wideband systems.

HCDR Technology Model

The thermal noise and dispersion fade margins of the target HCDRs must be established for use with the channel model in order to undertake link performance analysis. Potential designs for a radio capable of meeting requirements for the targeted wideband on-the-move application must consider technologies that match the channel characteristics and countermeasures that reduce the radio's sensitivity to time-varying dispersion. Trade-off studies between fundamental equipment alternatives, including bandwidth, modulation type, clock recovery and synchronization, error correction, transmitter power, antenna designs, and other key technologies, must be undertaken. Analysis of these technical issues will support an HCDR equipment model including antennas and follow-on simulations of HCDR links.

HCDR Link Performance Example

The anticipated results from the HCDR link-performance model can be demonstrated by a simple illustrative example to determine maximum path lengths for a range of propagation environments, different antenna sizes, and fixed terminals. The characteristics of the examples are 156 Mbps, 64 QAM, 40-MHz bandwidth, 6 GHz, 30-dBm transmitter power, 15 dB of dynamic equalization capability, and parabolic antennas. The thermal-noise threshold is -63.5 dBm for a BER of 10^{-5} . The path reliability target is 99.9 percent, which is equally allocated to dispersion and thermal noise, i.e., each should provide at least 99.95-percent path reliability. The probability of deep fading,

which is central to the channel model, is given by [1]

$$P = 10^{-5.12 C D^{3.6} F^{0.89} 10^{-A/10}}, A \geq 25$$

where

P = percentage of time during which fading of received signal exceeds depth A

A = fade depth relative to nonfaded signal (positive dB)

C = climate factor

D = path length (km)

F = radio frequency (GHz)

A climate factor, $C = 1$, is used for areas of average propagation (most of the continental United States [CONUS]). For difficult CONUS climates and terrains (e.g., the U.S. Gulf coast), $C = 10$ is used. The value of $C = 10$ is also appropriate for similar international climates and terrains. For worst-case conditions, $C = 100$ is used. This would be appropriate for cases of extreme heat and humidity, such as the Red Sea or Persian Gulf coastal plain or equatorial conditions [2]. It is assumed that the 15 dB of IBPD has the same occurrence probability as a 30-dB single-frequency fade. (The channel-modeling effort will provide a more accurate determination of IBPD probabilities for different climates.)

The maximum thermal-noise path lengths for a 64-QAM radio and 99.95-percent path reliability can be calculated from the equation for P for the different climate factors. The results are given in Table 2.

For difficult climates, thermal-noise-determined path lengths range from 30 to 14 km, depending on

Table 2. Thermal Noise Maximum Path Lengths

Climate	Climate Factor (C)	Transmitting Antenna Diameter, Feet	Receiving Antenna Diameter, Feet	Thermal-Noise Maximum Path Length, Kilometers	Thermal-Noise Fade Margin, dB	Reliability Reduced By Dispersion From 99.95%
Average	1	6	6	45.9	28.6	
	1	5	5	40.3	26.5	
	1	4	4	34.3	24.0	
	1	6	2	31.0	22.4	
	1	4	2	26.8	20.2	
	1	2	2	20.9	16.3	
Difficult	10	6	6	30.4	32.1	Yes
	10	5	5	26.7	30.1	Yes
	10	4	4	22.8	27.6	
	10	6	2	20.5	26.0	
	10	4	2	17.8	23.7	
	10	2	2	13.9	19.9	
Very Difficult	100	6	6	20.2	35.7	Yes
	100	5	5	17.7	33.7	Yes
	100	4	4	15.1	31.2	Yes
	100	6	2	13.6	29.6	
	100	4	2	11.8	27.3	
	100	2	2	9.2	23.4	

Notes:
64 QAM in 40 MHz bandwidth
Link reliability for thermal noise events, percent = 99.95
Transmitter power, dBm = 30

Receiver threshold, dBm = -63.5
Radio frequency, GHz = 6.0

antenna size. Dispersion will affect those path lengths that have required thermal-noise fade margins greater than 30 dB. Different equalization capabilities, of course, will affect the results. More thermal-noise capability will also be needed in order to meet the 40-km target in difficult climates. Such cost-capacity-technology and capability-reliability trade-offs will be provided.

The maximum dispersion path length for a 64-QAM radio and 99.95-percent path reliability can be calculated, assuming 15-dB dynamic-equalization capability and a 30-dB dispersive fade margin, from the equation for P for the different climate factors. The results are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Dispersion Maximum Path Lengths

Climate	Climate Factor C	Maximum Path Length, Kilometers
Average	1	50.3
Difficult	10	26.5
Very Difficult	100	14.0

Notes:

Reliability = 99.95 Percent, Frequency = 6.0 GHz
 Adaptive Dynamic Equalization Capability = 15 dB IBPD
 Dispersive Fade Margin = 30 dB

More equalization capability will be needed in order to meet the 20-km target for a 64-QAM radio in very difficult climates.

Conclusions

The models, recommendations, demonstrations, and prototypes resulting from this work will ensure that military communications systems and enhancements to these systems are planned, procured, and implemented to operate reliably and that maneuvering simulations include realistic communications effects. This will help avoid communications problems that can isolate commanders, soldiers, and automated battle-field systems.

References

1. K. H. Brockel et al., *Tactical Line-of-Sight Radio Propagation Reliability*, CECOM Technical Report TR-91-3, October 1991.
2. K. H. Brockel et al., *Tactical Line-of-Sight Path Reliability: Propagation Climate Factors*, CECOM Technical Report TR-92-9, October 1992.
3. K. H. Brockel et al., *NPT - A Success Story Evolving From Teamwork and Innovation*, MILCOM '93.
4. J. R. Mostow, Jr., et al., *NPT - The Tool for Planning MSE Networks*, MILCOM '94 (submitted).
5. W. C. Y. Lee, *Mobile Communications Engineering*, McGraw-Hill, 1982.
6. T. J. Wheeler et al., *Designing a Tactical ATM Network Integrating Performance Engineering and Design*, MILCOM '94 (submitted).